

Supporting information

Thermal Conductivity of a Supported Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotube

Fabian Könemann Morten Vollmann Tino Wagner
Norizzawati Mohd Ghazali Tomohiro Yamaguchi
Andreas Stemmer Koji Ishibashi Bernd Gotsmann

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1 MWCNT crystallinity

The electrical and thermal transport properties of MWNCTs depend on their crystal quality (crystallinity). In the article, we conclude that the reduction in thermal conductivity compared to values reported for free-standing MWCNTs is due to interactions with the substrate. We have performed transmission electron microscopy (TEM) on arc-discharge grown MWCNTs of the same type that was used to produce the device discussed in the article. fig. 1(a) shows such a TEM micrograph. The crystallinity of this MWCNT is high, as can be seen from the picture. As a comparison, fig. 1(b) shows a TEM result for an MWCNT that has been grown with chemical vapor deposition (CVD). The differences in crystal quality between the two growth approaches are evident from the two pictures. Based on this TEM study, we conclude that the MWCNT used for making the device is of close to perfect crystal quality and that the reduction in thermal conductivity is not due to a low crystallinity.

(a) Arc-discharge grown.

(b) CVD grown.

Figure 1: Transmission electron micrographs of an (a) arc-discharge grown MWCNT of the same type that was used to make the device discussed in the article, and a (b) CVD grown MWCNT. Individual shells are visible in the arc-discharge grown MWCNT as coherent straight lines, indicating the absence of defects. In comparison, the CVD grown MWCNT shows bending and shells that are splitting, merging and changing direction, which are indicators of low crystallinity.